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THE DEDICATION OF PHILIP V OF MACEDON IN THE LINDIAN CHRONICLE AND THE PROBLEMS OF ITS INTERPRETATION

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Abstract. In this paper is analyzed one record in epigraphic monument, found in the temple of Athena Lindia at the island of Rhodes. It is about a dedication by Philip V of Macedon (221 – 179 BC), which is read as follows: “King Philip: ten skirmisher shields, ten sarissas, ten helmets. On which has been inscribed: ‘King of the Macedonians, Philip, son of King Demetrius, having been victorious over the Dardanians and [the Maedians?], to Athena Lindia’, as the public records of the Lindians testify”. Commented are the different readings and the issues raised by the content of the inscription. It is accepted in historiography that there were two defeated ethnic groups: with some degree of probability the name of the Dardanians is restored, while from the second ethnonym not a single letter is legible. Methodological shortcomings of modern solutions for placing the information in a historical context are pointed out. It is assumed – according to the information from the Lindos Chronicle about a dedication of Alexander III the Great (336 – 323 BC) after a significant military victory – that Philip's successes must have been commensurate with these of Alexander. Thus, the dating of the battles conditionally to 204 BC is justified. Then, according to Diodorus, Philip V achieved a great victory over the Dardanians, that ended with 10,000 casualties. This victory is connected with an epigram of Antipater of Sidon, in which the Macedonian king is called “destroyer of the Dardanians”. At the same time, as it is suggested on the basis of fragments of Polybius, Philip V campaigned in Thrace. In one of these fragments the Thracians Digerri were mentioned; they inhabited near the Strymon (Struma) River. Unfortunately, the context of the information is unknown, but if it is really about military actions, as is suggested in the historiography, then it is unlikely that the Maedians have been remained unaffected. It is noted that a possible victory over the Maedians in 204 BC may explain their disappearance of ancient texts in the following decades.

Key words: *Hellenistic Age, Macedonia, Thracians.*

Introduction

The history of Thrace and the Thracians during the Hellenistic age is restored through limited sources. Therefore, modern historians try to extract information even from monuments of a more or less fragmented nature. A very good illustration of that conclusion is the so-called Lindian temple chronicle. This document is preserved in the form of a massive marble stela, originating from the Temple of Athens in Lindos, on the island of Rhodes. It is an official inscription prepared and published by decision of the city community and the officials of the temple (μαστροί) in 99 B.C. (Blinkenberg, 1941: 151-200; Higbie, 2003: 51 sq.; Bresson, 2006: 527-551; Massar, 2006: 229-243; Robert, 2010: 175-199). Its content is classified into four sections (see Figure 1) as follows: a decree for establishing this document (A), a list of gifts from legendary characters or historical figures received in the past (B – C) and stories of appearances (ἐπιφάνειαι) of the goddess Athena (D).

Special attention in relation with the history of the Balkans in Antiquity deserves the list of gifts received and the accompanying dedications. In the following lines only one of these records is considered (lines 127-131 of section C of the inscription, marked by the publishers as № XLII). This record transmits information about gifts from Philip V of Macedon (221 – 179 B.C.) and the reasons for their dedication (see an overview in Higbie, 2003: 41-43; Colosimo, 2017: 322-323). This, although scarce information, could be essential for the restoration of details of the Thracian policy of the Macedonian king.

victorious over the Dardanians [and the Maedians?], (dedicated) to Athena Lindia»; as the public records of the Lindians testify.

Due to the condition of this part of the monument, the letters are difficult to recognize (Figure 2). The penultimate row is badly damaged and it is not possible to read the names of the defeated ethnicities. This makes it difficult to place the inscription in a historical context, because there are no other elements, which can be used for a more concrete date of the events that were the reason for the dedication itself. On the basis of the distinguishable individual letters and the available space, two assumptions have been made for the restoration of the illegible part of the inscription.

Figure 2. Detail of the epigraphic monument with the dedication of Philip V
(Image source: Photo Archive of the National Museum of Denmark, Copenhagen)

In the first edition of the epigraphic monument Christian Blinkenberg suggested reading of the defeated peoples as Α[ἰτω]λ[ούς] and hence he proposed a relation with the Social War (220 – 217 B.C.), but that hypothesis was subsequently refuted (see Higbie, 2003: 140-141 with literature). In examining the same text Adolf Wilhelm suggested an alternative option: according to him, the victory was over the Dardanians and another one ethnicity, the Maedians or the Paeonians (Walbank, 1942: 138, not. 5; Higbie, 2003: 141 with literature). Wilhelm's idea was better aligned with the lacuna in the inscription, which allow deployment of no more than two names. It is particularly important to clarify that this author did not commit to a definitive restoration of the second ethnonym, insofar as its proposal reads: Δα[ρ]ῶ[ανί]ου[ς] καὶ Μαί[δα]ς *vel* Παίονας]. In a subsequent edition, Blinkenberg adopted the correction (Blinkenberg, 1941: 182), but he preferred to place in the empty space the Maedians, pointing out in support of this decision Livy's information for campaign of Philip V against them (Liv. 26.26.3 et 6) and an epigram of Antipater of Sidon (Anth. Pal. 6.115); both evidences are commented below. Some suspicion about this suggestion is perceptible in the

notes of subsequent publishers (Higbie, 2003: 141 – “The damage to the stone is so great in this entry that little can be said for certain about this votive, other than it was made by Philip to Athena after a victory”). In the same vein are also the comments of some researchers, who have worked with this monument (Papazoglu, 1978: 152-153). The poor state of the text is certainly the reason why no other editions have been suggested. In fact, the absence of alternative readings or comments is valid not only for this case, but even is marked as a critical note for the content of the entire inscription (Bresson, 2006: 528-529). Thus, in historiography the two ethnonyms from the penultimate line are recognized as “Dardanians and Maedians”. In any case, the absence of even a single preserved letter of the second ethnonym demonstrates its conditional recovery and leaves doubts on any identification assumptions. Same is true and for the idea recently expressed that the second name may be of inhabitants of a city, which could be Bylazora (Buqinca, 2021: 44).

It is worth noting that the verb “prevails” (νικάω), used in the dedication, does not allow to find out while the victory was in result of only one battle, i.e. the Dardanians and the second precariously restored ethnicity formed a common front against Philip V, or it comes about consecutive victories over two opponents in one campaign. In the current state of the studies the second seems more probable, because such united actions are not typical for the northern neighbors of the Macedonians: the Dardanians, as well as the Maedians, in most documented cases fought independently (a review of the political history of the Dardanians see in Papazoglu, 1978: 131-269; Mihajlović, 2018: 181-213; about the Maedians see Делев, 2014: 338-356).

Problems of the interpretation

The text of the inscription refers to a dedication by Philip V on the occasion of one or more military victories. Its interpretation relates to the clarification of three unknown circumstances: symbolism behind the dedication, date of the battles and identification of the defeated enemies.

Behind the dedication itself, there was certainly some sense, although it remains undissolved. It is hardly accidental to deposit three types of ten pieces of (protective and offensive) armament. No attempts to explain the symbolism of these gifts are found in historiography.

In Antiquity it was common after a military victory to dedicate trophy weapons in sanctuaries or temples (Mylonopoulos, 2013: 88 – “Any sanctuary could become a recipient of dedicated weapons; however, the Panhellenic sanctuaries occupy a special position in this regard”). Such cases are well documented in the Lindian chronicle (Shaya, 2005: 423-442), where it is also attested the practice of dedication of combat equipment by individuals (Higbie, 2003: 18-50). However, for the case of Philip V it is not explicitly mentioned that it comes about military trophies (for such an interpretation see Bresson, 2006: 546), although it seems likely. Even if this is true, each of the three types of weapons was also used in the Macedonian army in the time of Philip V and cannot serve as an ethnic scar to identify the defeated ones.

It is unknown why the weapons were of three types and exactly ten pieces in number. Legendary evidence from the same document provides some guidelines for thinking: “*Τοι μετὰ Τλαπολέμου εἰς Ἴλιον [στρατευσά]μενοι ἀσπίδας ἑννῆ, ἐνχειρίδια [ἑννῆ, κυνᾶς] ἰ ἑννῆ, κναμίδων ζεύγη ἑννῆ· ἐ[πεγέγραπτο] | δὲ ἐπὶ τᾶν ἀσπίδων· “τοὶ μετ[ὰ Τλαπολέμου] ἰ εἰς Ἴλιον στρατευσάμενοι τ[ᾶ] Ἀθάναι τ[ᾶ]ι | Λινδαῖαι ἀκροθίνια τῶν ἐκ Τροί[ας], ὡς φασι Γόρ[γ]λων ἐν τᾶι α τᾶν περὶ Ῥόδου, Γ[ο]ργοσθέν[η]ς | ἐν τᾶι ἐπιστολαῖ, Ἱερόβουλος [ἐν τᾶι ἐπιστολαῖ] / The man making an expedition with Tlapolemos against Ilion: nine shields, nine daggers, nine leather caps, nine pairs of greaves. It had been inscribed on the shields, «the men making an expedition with Tlapolemos against Ilion to Athena the Lindian, spoils [of those] from Troy», as Gorgon states in the eleventh book of his work «About Rhodes», Gorgosthenes in his letter, Hieroboulos in his letter” (English translation after Higbie, 2003: № IX). To unravel the symbolism behind this dedication the modern scientists used information from the Homer's*

Iliad (Hom., II., 2.653-6), according to which the Rhodians sent against the Trojans nine ships under the command of Παπολέμος (Higbie, 2003: 86).

No key is found for explanation of Philip V's dedication, which could potentially direct to reasonable explanation of the gifts, dedicated by the Macedonian king. On this issue do not fully help the preserved records in the same document for dedications of predecessors of Philip V on the Macedonian throne. Before him, Alexander III the Great (336 – 323 B.C.) placed gifts in the same sanctuary after a military victory: “βασιλεὺς Ἀλέξανδρος [β]ο[υ]κέφαλα, ἐφ’ ὧν [ἐ]πιέγραπται | “βασιλεὺς Ἀλέξανδρος μάχαι κρατήσας Δαρείον και κύριος γε[ν]όμενος τῆς Ἀσίας ἔθυσσε τ[ᾶ]ι Ἀθάναι τᾶι [Λι]νδίαι κατὰ μαντείαν | ἐπ’ ἰε[ρ]έ[ω]ς Θεουγέν[ε]υς τοῦ Πιστοκράτευς”. Πεῖρι τ[ρ]ούτων το[ῖ] Λινδί[ων] χρηματισμοὶ περι[ί]έχοντι. | ἀν[έ]θηκε δὲ και [ᾗ]πλα, ἐφ’ ὧν ἐπιέγραπται. / King Alexander: caltrops. On which has been inscribed «King Alexander having overcome in battle Darius and becoming lord of Asia, offered sacrifice to Athena the Lindian according to an oracle during the priesthood [held] by Theugenes, the son of Pistokrateus». These things the public records of the Lindians contain. And he also dedicated armour, on which there is an inscription“ (English translation after Higbie, 2003: № XXXVIII). It is suggested that the imitation of Alexander III the Great was one of the motives of the next kings to dedicate gifts to the sanctuary, including for Philip V (Massar, 2006: 239).

It is also problematic to date the victory or the victories from the dedication of Philip V. As a *terminus ante quem* is indicated 202 B.C., when it comes to war between Macedonia and Rhodes (Walbank, 2014: 268, not. 6), but other researchers add that the relationships between these two states were tense from the outset (Higbie, 2003: 141). As a result of the latter ascertainment, the presence of a dedication by Philip V is explained by his royal status; it was not motivated by political or diplomatic reasons, related with the history of the island (Massar, 2006: 238).

A suggestion is proposed for a relation of the victories from the inscription with the campaign of the Macedonian king against the Maedians in 211 B.C. (Papazoglu, 1978: 152; Делев, 2014: 343). It seems that main motive for this assumption was the absence of any other direct information in the ancient literature about victory of Philip V over the Maedians. The expedition in question was described with sufficient details by Titus Livy (Liv. 26.25.5-8, 26.25.15). The ancient historian reported, prior to follow-up the operations against the Maedians, for actions of the Macedonian king in Illyria, after which he changed the direction of his march to Pelagonia, where he conquered an unnamed city, used for incursions into Macedonia (Liv. 26.25.3-4; for the correct reading of this information according to the manuscript tradition see Митрев, 2019: 5-17). Apparently, that year the Macedonian ruler secured his northern borders, before heading south (for the usual nature of this practice see Walbank, 2014: 85). However, the information reported cannot serve to a key for deciphering the dedication from Lindos, which raises doubts whether it is possible to link these two sources, the Lindian chronicle and the text of Livy, to one and the same events.

Recently is proposed an explanation with the victory over the Dardanians and the capture of Bylazora in 217 B.C. (Buqinca, 2021: 44), reported by Polybius (Polyb. 5.97.1-2); the Dardanians used Bylazora as main point for their incursions into Macedonia and after this act of the Macedonian king the Dardanian threat has been neutralized for several years. No arguments have been put forward in support of that hypothesis.

Alternative possibilities for identifying the victory or the victories have not been discussed, although there are some other ancient evidences about military actions of Philip V against the Dardanians. They can be arranged chronologically (from the beginning of the reign of the Macedonian king up to 202 B.C.) as follows:

- 220 B.C.: the Dardanians and the other Macedonian neighbors, including some Thracians, which were not named by name, invaded the domains of the Macedonian king, but he successfully dealt with this danger (Илиев, 2021: 305-311);
- 217 B.C.: the already mentioned victory over the Dardanians and the capture of Bylazora (Papazoglu, 1978: 150-151);

- 211 B.C.: this campaign against the Maedians has also been commented on above;
- 209 B.C. (summer of): the Dardanians entered Macedonia, motivated by hearing about the death of Philip V; clashes with them appear to have continued into the following year (Papazoglu, 1978: 153-154; Walbank, 2014: 97-98), without being known whether it concerns two separate campaigns or a continuation of last year's;
- 207/206 B.C.: there was, according to the interpretation of an epigraphic monument, expedition against the Dardanians (Papazoglu, 1978: 154); probably the same was mentioned by Titus Livy (Liv. 28.8.14);
- 204 B.C.: Philip V undertook *“ἐστράτευσε δ̄ ἐπὶ Δαρδάνους οὐδ̄ ν̄ ἀδικοῦντας, καὶ τούτους παρατάξει νικήσας ἀνείλεν ὑπ̄ ρ̄ τοὺς μυρίους / expedition against the Dardanians, even though they did nothing wrong to him; he defeated them in a great battle, ended with over 10,000 people killed”* (Diod. 28.2.1). Diodorus's information can explain the epigram of Antipater of Sydon, in which the Macedonian king was called *“Δαρδανέων ὀλετήρ / destroyer of the Dardanians”* (Anth. Pal., 6.115). Another ancient message can be associated with the same event: in Justin's epitome of Pompeius Trogus explicitly are mentioned the calls of the Macedonians to their king for revenge against their neighbors immediately after the end of the First Macedonian war (215 – 205 B.C.), and Philip V could not decide which of these calls to respond first (Iust. 29.4.5-9). According to the same text *„Prima tamen illi expeditio adversus Dardanos fuit, qui absentiam eius aucupantes maiore belli mole Macedoniae iminebant / his first expedition was against the Dardanians, which, watching his absence, were ready to hit Macedonia with even greater powers [than before]”* (Iust. 29.4.10).

Most enigmatic and at the same time on an unusually large scale among the listed – if the reported data are correct – was the victory for which Diodorus writes. Some scholars dated it to 204 B. C. (Walbank, 2014: 111), others – to 202 B.C. (Danov, 1979: 78). In both years Philip V fought in Thrace: in the first year only presumed, based on the fragments of Polybius, and in the second – conquered some cities along the Thracian Aegean coast (Danov, 1979: 78; Делев, 2017: 39). It is more likely that the victory was in 204 B.C., because in 202 B.C. the attention of the Macedonian king was directed to the Eastern Mediterranean, which implies that the borders with traditional adversaries have been well secured.

Conclusions

The dedication of Philip V from the Lindian temple chronicle, analyzed in this paper, along with the commented opinions and assumptions about its content, led to formulation of several substantial observations.

First of all, the current state of the epigraphic monument does not allow definitive identification of the ethnicities, defeated by Philip V. With a certain degree of probability, the Dardanians have been restored, but for the second ethnonym – of which not a single letter is preserved – only assumptions are possible.

In the publications of modern scientists, there is a methodical disadvantage of the attempts for identification of the victory or the victories, initiated in the dedication: only solutions are proposed, without support by factual arguments. Therefore, the hypotheses expressed appear to be completely random. For the proposed identification of the defeated as „Dardanians and Maedians“ ancient sources of completely different events are combined: the story about the march against the Maedians in 211 B.C. and the epigram of Antipater of Sydon, which – as was already noted – is rather result of an event, happened in 204 B.C. The operation against Dardanians and Maedians in 211 B.C. did not appear to be sufficiently effective, because as early as 207 B.C. they were again a threat to Macedonia. The second assumption presented in historiography, about the Dardanians and the inhabitants of Bylazora, also does not seem very likely.

There are no attempts for interpretation of the dedication in the context of the other records from the Lindian chronicle. It is possible that the dedication of Alexander III the Great

really was among the motives for that of Philip V. If this is true, the scale and importance of his victory or victories should have been commensurable with those of Alexander's. In this way, the usual border clashes should be excluded as explanation. A much more likely is relation with the extraordinary victory, mentioned by Diodorus; it makes sense that the designation of Philip V as "destroyer of the Dardanians" was in result of this victory.

Something more, it is quite possible that the Maedians suffered a devastating defeat between 206 – 202 B.C. Both Polybius and Livy report readiness of the Thracians bordering Macedonia, among them mostly the Maedians, to invade the country in 207 B.C. (Polyb. 10.41.4; Liv. 28.5.7). This is their last registered presence in the available ancient sources up to the end of Philip V's reign; since then, the Maedians disappeared for a long time from the sight of the ancient writers and nothing is known about them (see the sources in Делев, 2014: 344-345). A victory over them in the supposed Thracian march of the Macedonian king, commonly dated by the scholars in 204 B.C., provides a convincing explanation of this fact. An additional argument in this relation can be the mention of the Digerri in one of the available fragments of Polybius (Polyb. 13, fr. 10.9), on the basis of which the march in question is supposed to be derived. Unfortunately, the context is unknown, but if it really is about military actions, there is no way that the Maedians could not have been affected, because the Digerri were also located near the Strymon (Struma) River, according to information of Pliny the Elder (Plin., Nat. Hist., 4.11.40).

It seems that the number of the dedicated gifts was preordained by traditions of the sanctuary, as far as are documented and other dedications, composed of a specific number of weapons. Nevertheless, their semantics remain unclear next to finding a key to unravel them.

The necessary summary in result of the analysis carried out in this paper is that the Lindian chronicle most likely contains a dedication of Philip V on the occasion of great victories over Dardanians and Thracian (mostly Maedians) maybe in 204 B.C. The act of the dedication must have happened immediately after the victories; this meets the condition for a date before the escalation of tensions between Philip V and Rhodes, turned into a war in 202 B.C. Such an explanation is in line with the policy of the Macedonian king until 204 – 203 B.C., consisting in the avoid of an open conflict with the Rhodians and hostile actions against them through intrigues and dummies (Walbank, 2014: 112). No less important is that the proposed hypothesis explains the absence of Maedians from events in the coming decades.

Literature

Делев, П. История на племената в Югозападна Тракия през I хил. пр. Хр. София: Унив. изд. „Св. Климент Охридски“, 2014.

Делев, П. Древна Тракия в края на III и през първата половина на II в. пр. Хр. Сборник в чест на XX години програми по египтология в Нов български университет. София: Изток-Запад, 2017, 36-50.

Илиев, Й. Военни действия на Филип V Македонски срещу траките през Съюзническата война (220 – 217 г. пр. Хр.). Годишна международна научна конференция на Висше военновъздушно училище „Георги Бенковски“ 2021. Сборник доклади. Долна Митрополия: ВВВУ „Г. Бенковски“, 2021, 305-311.

Митрев, Г. По следите на несъществуващата Дарданска Синтия: Liv. 26.25.3. Пловдивски исторически форум, 3(2), 2019, 5-17.

Blinkenberg, Chr. Lindos. Fouilles et recherches, 1902-1914. Vol. II, Inscriptions. Tome I (Nos. 1 – 281). Berlin & Copenhagen: Walter de Gruyter & G. E. C. Gad, 1941, <https://doi.org/10.11588/diglit.52557>

Bresson, A. Relire la Chronique du temple lindien. *Topoi*, 14(2), 2006, 527-551.

Buqinca, A. Recherche sur les Dardaniens: VIe-ler siècles av. J.-C. Thèse de doctorat de l'Université de Lyon, 2021, <<https://tel.archives-ouvertes.fr/tel-03248733>> [03.12.2021]

Colosimo, N. M. Reconstructing the Dedicatory Experience: Flexibility and Limitation in the Ancient Greek Dedicatory Process. PhD Thesis. Bryn Mawr College, 2017, <<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/214024339.pdf>> [03.12.2021]

Danov, Chr. M. Die Thraker auf dem Ostbalkan von der hellenistischen Zeit bis zur Gründung Konstantinopels, *Aufstieg und Niedergang der römischen Welt*, Geschichte und Kultur Roms in Spiegel der neueren Forschung, II. Berlin & New York: Walter De Gruyter, 1979, 21-185.

Higbie, C. The Lindian Chronicle and the Greek Creation of Their Past. Oxford & New York: Oxford University Press, 2003.

Massar, N. La «Chronique de Lindos»: un catalogue à la gloire du sanctuaire d'Athéna Lindia. *Kernos: Revue internationale et pluridisciplinaire de religion grecque antique*, 19, 2006, 229-243, <https://doi.org/10.4000/kernos.452>

Mihajlović, V. D. Roman Imperialism and the Construction of Dardanian Collectivity. Marko A. Janković, Vladimir D. Mihajlović (eds.). *Reflections of Roman Imperialisms*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2018, 181-213.

Mylonopoulos, J. Greek Sanctuaries as Places of Communication through Rituals: An Archaeological Perspective. Eftychia Stavrianopoulou (ed.). *Ritual and Communication in the Graeco-Roman World*. Liège: Presses universitaires de Liège, 2013, 69-110, <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.pulg.1125>

Papazoglu, F. The Central Balkan tribes in Pre-Roman times. Amsterdam: Adolf M. Hakkert, 1978.

Robert, R. Histoire d'objets. Objets d'histoire. *Dialogues d'histoire ancienne* – supplement 4.1, 2010, 175-199.

Shaya, J. The Greek Temple as Museum: The Case of the Legendary Treasure of Athena from Lindos. *American Journal of Archaeology*, 109(3), 2005, 423-442.

Walbank, F. W. Alcaeus of Messene, Philip V, and Rome. *The Classical Quarterly*, 36 (3/4), 134-145.

Walbank, F. W. Philip V of Macedon. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014.

ПОСВЕЩЕНИЕТО НА ФИЛИП V МАКЕДОНСКИ В ЛИНДОСКАТА ХРОНИКА И ПРОБЛЕМИТЕ НА НЕГОВАТА ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ

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Резюме. В предлагания доклад е анализиран един от записите в епиграфски документ, произхождащ от светилището на Атина Линдоска на о. Родос, познат като Линдоска хроника. Става дума за посвещение на Филип V Македонски (221 – 179 г. пр. Хр.), което се чете: „Цар Филип: десет леки щита, десет сариса, десет шлема. На тях е написано: «Царят на македоните Филип, син на цар Деметрий, след като победи дарданите и [медите?], (посвети) на Атина Линдоска»; така пише в Линдоските обществени записи“. Коментирани са предложените разночетения и проблемите, които съдържанието на надписа поставя. В историографията е прието, че победените етноси били два: с известна степен на вероятност са възстановени дарданите, докато от втория етноним не е запазена нито една буква. Посочени са методически недостатъци на съвременните решения за поставяне на сведението в исторически контекст. На базата на информацията от Линдоската хроника за посвещение на Александър III Велики след значима военна победа е предположено, че Филиповите успехи трябва да са били съизмерими с Александровите. Така е обоснована датировка на сраженията условно към 204 г. пр. Хр. Тогава, според сведение на Диодор, Филип V постигнал голяма победа над дарданите, завършила с над 10 хил. убити. Тази победа е свързана с епиграма на Антипатър от Сидон, в която македонският цар бил наречен „унищожител на дарданите“. По същото време, както се предполага въз основа на фрагменти на Полибий, Филип V воювал и в Тракия. В един от фрагментите били споменати траките дигери, които живеели край р. Стримон (Струма). За съжаление контекстът на сведението е неизвестен, но ако наистина се касае за военни действия, както се предполага в историографията, тогава медите няма как да не са били засегнати. Отбелязано е, че евентуална победа над медите през 204 г. пр. Хр. може да обясни тяхното изчезване от античните текстове през следващите десетилетия.

Ключови думи: *елинистическа епоха, Македония, траки.*

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